

Pre Survey for Zooniverse GWitchHunters

REINFORCE
REsearch INfrastructures FOR Citizens in Europe

Information on study

With your help, we want to learn about the impact of the GWitchHunters (<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/reinforce/gwitchhunters>) project on Zooniverse, to gain a better understanding of participants' interest in science and nature, the motivation for joining and the impact on science skills and knowledge. In order to detect changes in these areas we ask you to fill in two questionnaires, the current one for now and a similar one in about two months.

The study is supported by the EU funded project Reinforce (<https://www.reinforceeu.eu>), which aims to bring Research Infrastructures closer to citizens.

Please help us to learn! Your feedback and input is very much appreciated!

It takes only 15-20 min of your time!

How will your data be used?

Your feedback will inform the overall learning and evaluation of GWitchHunters (<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/reinforce/gwitchhunters>). The aggregated results of the analysis will be published and a link will be posted at www.reinforceeu.eu (<https://www.reinforceeu.eu>). Please note, your responses will be anonymised and we will not ask to give your name. We ask however to reveal your email-address to **contact you again in about two months** for another similar survey. Your email address will be deleted as soon as the data has been compiled to make the dataset completely anonymous. We will also receive access statistics to the project through Zooniverse. All the information will be kept in a password protected file and the data collected will be destroyed once the research work has been finalised.

If you have a concern about any aspect of the evaluation, feel free to contact us per email: fabian@zsi.at. For Zooniverse's User Agreement and Privacy Policy, please visit www.zooniverse.org/privacy. For further details about how your data will be used in this survey, see the Privacy Notice.

There are 22 questions in this survey.

Consent

You may refuse to participate or withdraw your participation at any time without providing any reasons. Your participation in the study is highly valued and will definitely make a significant contribution. Without a considerable number of participants, this study will be compromised.

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Please express your consent to allow us to process your data as described above by clicking here

If you are under 16 years old, please ask one of your parents/guardians for permission to participate in this survey and tick this box.

To measure the personal effect, we ask you to give us the permission to contact you again in about two months to fill in a similar questionnaire. Please share the email-address that you have used to sign up with on Zooniverse to get meaningful results.

Please type in your Zooniverse email-address:

*

Please write your answer here:

Please type in your Zooniverse nickname: *

Please write your answer here:

Attitude towards science

Please indicate how much you **DISAGREE** or **AGREE** with each of the following statements. Please respond as **YOU** really feel, rather than how you think “most people” feel – there are no ‘right’ and ‘wrong’ answers.

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	<i>strongly disagree</i>	<i>disagree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>strongly agree</i>
I am interested in learning more about the universe.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I like to engage in science-related hobbies in my free time.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I often visit science-related web sites.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I enjoy learning about new scientific discoveries or inventions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other people would describe me as a “science person”.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am very interested in the natural sciences.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I enjoy reading about science-related topics.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I enjoy talking about science topics with others.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	<i>strongly disagree</i>	<i>disagree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>strongly agree</i>
I enjoy looking at information presented in scientific tables and graphs.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Why did you choose to participate in the GWitchHunters project?
(multiple answers possible). *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	<i>strongly disagree</i>	<i>disagree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>strongly agree</i>
Because I think it's a good idea.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Because I enjoy doing it.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Because I believe that I can contribute to scientific research.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Because I enjoy getting involved in scientific activities.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Because I am fascinated that I might help to make discoveries.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am interested in connecting the work with my professional activities, e.g. teaching in my class.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Because people I look up to think it's a good thing.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Because the topic is really important to me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	<i>strongly disagree</i>	<i>disagree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>strongly agree</i>
For the recognition I get from others.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Because I like the international environment.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Because I want to dedicate my spare time to something meaningful.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
For other reasons.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please describe shortly for which other reasons you chose to participate.

Please write your answer here:

Science skills

Please begin each statement below with: “*I currently have the skills necessary to...*” *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	<i>strongly disagree</i>	<i>disagree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>strongly agree</i>
understand how to categorise the data of the GWitchHunters project.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
interpret the meaning of the data.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
communicate project findings to others.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
train others to participate in the project.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
design a study related to the project data.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

These statements are about how you feel about doing (citizen) science activities *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	<i>strongly disagree</i>	<i>disagree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>strongly agree</i>
I think I'm pretty good at following instructions for scientific activities.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Compared to other people my age, I think I can do scientific activities pretty well.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It takes me a long time to understand how to do scientific activities.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel confident about my ability to explain how to do scientific activities to others.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Knowledge

In this section, we would like to understand how familiar you are with the scientific work and terms of the GWitchHunters project. This is not a test, and we hope that you feel free to provide your answers without hesitation. It is okay, not to know everything!

I would know how to **explain** the following terms in simple words: *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	<i>strongly disagree</i>	<i>disagree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>strongly agree</i>
Citizen Science	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research infrastructures	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Machine learning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gravitational waves	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Neutrino	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cosmic rays	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interferometer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Signal and noise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Glitch	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Spectrogram	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

I would know how to **explain** the following terms in simple words: *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	<i>strongly disagree</i>	<i>disagree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>strongly agree</i>
Waveform	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Rate	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Black hole	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Neutron star	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Supernova	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Elementary particle	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Radioactivity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Virgo	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

In your opinion, what is true and what is false?

The main aim of the research carried out in large research infrastructures such as CERN, KM3NeT or VIRGO is:

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	<i>true</i>	<i>false</i>	<i>don't know</i>
Understanding the universe from the very small to the very big.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Creating a replication of the Big Bang in the laboratory.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Producing industrial applications.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Offering solutions for the betterment of society.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Hidden because they don't want us to know what is really happening.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Opening portals to other dimensions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	<i>true</i>	<i>false</i>	<i>don't know</i>
Producing military applications, e.g. creating high tech weapons.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

In your opinion, what is true and what is false?

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	<i>true</i>	<i>false</i>	<i>don't know</i>
'Spacetime' can ripple.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electrons are smaller than atoms.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Humans, as we know them today, evolved from earlier species of animals.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Light travels faster than sound.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Black holes are extremely compact stars.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Noise can impact on a scientific measure.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
New instruments can be designed to face new challenges in science.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Classified data can help to identify new galaxies.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Access to Zooniverse

6a. How did you learn about the GWitchHunters project on Zooniverse?
(multiple answers possible)

*

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Through a Reinforce event
- Through other people
- Through my work/school
- Social media
- Reinforce webpage
- Because I found it on Zooniverse

Other:

In which Reinforce event did you participate? (multiple answers possible)

*

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Webinar
- Vision building workshop
- Training
- Practice reflection
- Workshops
- Summer/winter school
- Science café
- Open schooling day
- Demonstration of project
- Pilot days
- Open Lab day

Other:

Some questions about you

What is your highest level of education? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Primary education
- Secondary/high school
- Vocational training
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- PhD or other advanced professional degree

What is your current employment status? (multiple answers possible)

*

Please choose **all** that apply:

Full time employed

Part time employed

Unemployed

Student

Retired

Other:

Do you have a professional background in science? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

Not sure

What is your age? *

Please write your answer here:

With which gender do you identify? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

Do you have a visual impairment (if you can see well with visual aids, that doesn't count)? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

Do you feel being part of a discriminated-against group? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, based on which of the following? (multiple answers possible) *

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Gender
- Sexual orientation
- Race
- Migration history (1st and 2nd generation)
- Religion
- Disability
- Other

You have successfully completed the survey and your responses have been recorded.

Thank you very much once again for your time!

Your response is very valuable to us!

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.